

RADIO CONTROL PORTABLE TEA HARVESTER TO ACCELERATE PLUCKING AND REJUVENATION OF TEA LEAVES

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Abstract

The industrial revolution 4.0 demands integrated industrial automation in various aspects, one of which is in the tea plantation industry. The tea plantation industry had previously known several automations in its development, as example is the automation of picking tea leaves which usually use tea harvester machines. Tea harvester usually operated by 2 to 4 people. Portable radio control tea harvester is a research of making smaller harvester than usual that can be operated only 1 person and has an integrated system using radio control signals that can send data on the actual condition and position of the tea harvester used in the GCS (Ground Control Station). Portable tea harvester control radio equipped with sensors that will monitor the condition of the device and the Global Positioning System (GPS) that will track the tool, so that if this tool is mass produced then the owner of the tea garden that has a large portable tea harvester can see the position of the tool is being used on a digital garden map on the Central Control Room (CCR) in a tea company portable tea harvester users.

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1. Introduction

Tea plantation industry is a labor-intensive type of business that can absorb a large workforce. Nationally, in Indonesia the tea industry contributes around 1.2 trillion Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (0.3% of total non-oil and gas GDP) and contributes net foreign exchange of around 110 million US dollars per year (Agricultural Information System and Data Center, 2015). From an environmental aspect, tea cultivation and processing is a type of business that supports soil and water conservation (ATI, 2000). However, there are several aspects in the tea plantation that need to be automated to support performance and synchronize plantation workers. The Industrial Revolution 4.0 demands integrated automation from various fields that make work done routinely by humans can be helped by an automated system that is monitored. In tea plantations, several methods have been developed that implement the automation system, one of which is in picking tea leaves. Generally, picking tea in Indonesia is done using 2 methods, the first method is manually picked with human labor and the second is picked using machines controlled by human. Automation carried out on tea picking using machines is usually limited to harvesting by waring and transport methods. Radio control harvester is a method for monitoring tea picking by monitoring the performance of the tea harvester equipment that is being operated. Monitoring carried out by sending sensor data that provides several indicators of equipment conditions, such as the position of the equipment in the plantation, the duration of use the device, and the temperature of the machine. Through the prototype of this portable tea picking machine, it is expected to be created farmer regeneration on a plantation scale, applying the concept of automatic tools to accelerate and facilitate harvesting and prevent harvesting from

being wasted on the ground, applying the industry 4.0 concept to the plantation industry, and monitoring the productivity of picking tea in a plantation

2.Literature Review

2.1. Tea Harvester

Tea harvester is a tea cutting tool that is commonly used in picking tea leaves. Tea harvester usually uses a motor that is fueled by gasoline or diesel fuel, which will drive the cutting blade so that it can pick the leaf automatically.

Figure1. Tea Harvester

Tea leaves cutting takes several principles such as picking, rejuvenating, and storing so the growth of tea leaves can be sustained.

2.2. Xbee Pro

Xbee Pro is a radio frequency module that can transmit data using serial communication. In Xbee, tea harvester radio control is useful for sending sensor data and location data obtained from GPS. Xbee can communicate pair to pair or directly displayed on the interface.

Figure 2. Xbee Pro

2.3. Interface

U-Center is an interface that is used to display sensor data and locations that have been obtained. Through this interface the garden owner can monitor the performance of the tool and see the position of the tool being used.

2.4. Sensor

There are several sensors installed on the tea harvester, the sensor is used to monitor the condition of the equipment so that treatment can be carried out regularly within a certain period.

2.4.1. LM35

LM35 is a temperature sensor that will monitor the temperature of the engine so that if the engine overheats it can be detected earlier. The LM35 is placed near the carburetor engine to detect heat faster in the engine.

2.4.2. RTC

To detect how long the device is used the RTC sensor calculates the accumulated time from the engine turned on. Then time detection data can be displayed in the interface at the ground control station.

2.4.3. Gps Module

Detection of the tool position on the plantation map is using a GPS module. The GPS module will detect the attitude axis and the latitude of the map coordinates, then the coordinate data is sent using radio frequency.

3. Equipment Testing Methods

3.1. Equipment Testing Scenario

The design of the test aims to systemize all the experiments that will be carried out, the procedure testing design can be seen in table 1. as shown below

Table 1. Testing Scenario

No	Testing Scenario	Objectives
1	Turn the main machine by pulling the carburetor lever	Machine turned on and rolls the motor of cutting blade
2	The cutting blade slides on it's path, so it cuts the tea leaves and pushes it to the container box	Harvesting the tea leaves
3	When main machine is activated, the gps and other electronic devices is also activated	Sensor and GPS will monitor the current temperature and it's position in the field
4	Data is sent using frequency radio through Xbee Module	Field-monitoring data acquired so that it could be

		recorded
5	Display the results of sensor and GPS monitoring on the interface	So the owner of the plantation area could supervise workers who operate the equipment

Figure 3. Equipment Performance Flow Chart

The equipment operating procedure is done by pulling the carburetor lever to activate the main machine. After the main machine has activated, the electronic device can be activated so GPS could plot the location. When the gas throttle is pulled, the motor will roll and move the cutting blades to harvest tea leaves by cutting its leaves. When harvesting process occurs, the installed GPS and sensor will monitorize the condition of equipment that being used. Furthermore, GPS will detect the equipment's movement on the field that can be seen through a computer called Ground Control Station (GCS). The tea leaves that have been cut will then enter the container box, and after the container box is full, the harvest is then thrown into the sack and weighed by the workers.

4.Data and Analysis

The mechanical system of Tea Harvester was made by designing whole basic system drawings, then the drawings can be used to design the specific gear system. However, the creation of the system actually also considering the ergonomic value of the equipment, so then the final result of the equipment will be slightly different from the first design that has been made.

4.1. Mechanical System Form Analysis

The mechanical system of tea harvester was first made by designing system engineering drawings, the technique was the reference for making the real system. However, the creation of the system actually also takes into account the ergonomic value of the tool, so that the results into the tool are actually slightly different from the system design that has been made.

Figure 4 Basic Design of Machine Mechanical System

After ergonomic and efficiency calculation of the equipment has done, the final design is obtained with the shape and infographics of the tool as shown in Figure 4.2 as follows

Figure 5 Overall Design of Tea Harvester

4.2. Manually-Harvested Tea Leaves Data

The data of Manually-Harvested tea leaves are obtained by counting the amounts of the hand-picked tea leaves for an amount of time

Table 1. Tea Harvesting Data Using Manually

No	Weight	Time
1	104,16 grams	1 minute

2	6250 grams	60 minute
3	31250 grams	300 minute
4	50000 grams	480 minute

Table 2. Tea Harvesting Data Using Tea Harvester

No	Weight	Time
1	118 grams	1 minute
2	7,08 grams	60 minute
3	35,4 grams	300 minute
4	56,64 grams	480 minute

Data taken in units of time is the data weighing from the leaves in the box of the Tea Harvester, and not the data from weighing the whole harvesting model.

4.4. GPS and Data Sensor from Interface

Sensor data that has been taken can be monitored through a computer that functions as GCS, the GPS used will also track the position of the equipment used through the obtained attitude and latitude data and then displayed through the U-Center interface

Figure 4 Tracking GPS Interface Display

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